

Comparative study of stress and immune-related transcript outcomes triggered by *Vibrio anguillarum* bacterin and air exposure stress in liver and spleen of gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata*), zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) and rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*)

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Abstract

The stress and immune-related effects of short-term (1, 6 and 24 h) air exposure stress (1 min), bath [vaccination](#) with [Vibrio anguillarum bacterin](#), and both stressors combined were evaluated in liver and spleen of [Sparus aurata](#), [Danio rerio](#) and [Oncorhynchus mykiss](#). Expression profiles of immune ([interleukin 1 beta: *il1β*](#); [tumor necrosis factor alpha: *tnfa*](#); [interleukin 10: *il10*](#); [tumor growth factor beta: *tgfβ1*](#); [immunoglobulin M: *igm*](#); [lysozyme: *lys*](#); [complement protein c3: *c3*](#)) and stress-related genes ([glucocorticoid receptor: *gr*](#); [heat shock protein 70: *hsp70*](#); and [enolase](#)) were analysed by RT-qPCR. [Cortisol](#) level was assessed by [radioimmunoassay](#). The gene expression patterns in liver and spleen were found to be differentially regulated in a time- and organ-dependent manner among species. In [seabream](#), a higher [*il1β*-driven inflammatory response](#) was recorded. In zebrafish, air exposure stress but not bath [vaccination](#) alone modulated most of the changes in liver and spleen immune transcripts. Stressed and vaccinated trout showed an intermediate pattern of gene expression, with a lower upregulation of immune-related genes in liver and the [absence](#) of changes in the expression of [hsp70](#) and [enolase](#) in spleen (as it was observed in [seabream](#) but not in zebrafish). Following air exposure, cortisol levels increased in plasma 1 h post-stress (hps) and then decreased at 6 hps in *O. mykiss* and *D. rerio*. By contrast, in *S. aurata* the cortisol level remained higher at 6 hps suggesting a greater degree of responsiveness to this stressor. When fish were exposed to combined air exposure plus bath vaccination cortisol levels were also augmented at 1 and 6 hps in *O. mykiss* and *S. aurata* and restored to basal level at 24 hps, whereas in *D. rerio* the response was higher in response to the combination of both stressors. In addition, *V. anguillarum* [bacterin](#) vaccination triggered [cortisol secretion](#) only in *D. rerio*, suggesting a greater responsiveness of *D. rerio* hypothalamic-pituitary-interrenal axis. Overall, comparing the tissue transcription responsiveness, liver was found to be more

implicated in the response to handling stress compared to spleen. These results also indicate that a species-specific response accounts for the deviations of stress and immune onset in the liver and spleen in these fish species.